

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: MOGOLLON****FIRST NAME: NESTOR****PROGRAM CODE: DME****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 6****INSTRUCTOR: DR. GULMA****Edit or delete text to show the actual information below:**

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author did use Zotero to insert references

The author did use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID).

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: 9%

The author used the following software: (MSWord 2016 on Windows 8)

ACA-401D QUIZ

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1. What are the factors contributing to successful dissertation research?

- Good communication, good planning, effective process for writing, attention to detail, openness to serendipity.¹
- Good planning, a good writing style, openness to serendipity, and literature review.
- Dissertation concept paper, dissertation prospectus, dissertation, and dissertation manuscript.
- Good communication, effective writing process, attention to detail, and good planning skills.

¹ James Sampson, *A Guide to Quantitative and Qualitative Dissertation Research*, 2nd ed., (Tallahassee: Florida State University, 2017), 13.

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2. What are the components of a dissertation abstract?

- Results, findings, problem statement, and methodology.
- Problem statement, research questions and hypotheses (if used), variable measures, procedures, findings, and implications.**²

3. What statements mention the correct use of the comma?

- Combine two sentences in one, divide adjectives not forming a series, and separate items in a series.
- To separate items in a series, link clauses, set off phrases and clauses, and separate adjectives in a series.**³
- Separate adjectives in a series, before, etc., and combine two sentences in one.
- Divide adjectives not forming a series to separate items in a series and always separate a main clause from the subordinate clause.

4. Which statements include the correct plural of these words: addendum, bacterium, consortium, genus, and medium?

- Addendums, bacteria, consortium, mediums, geneses.
- Addenda, bacteria, consortia, genera, media.**⁴
- Addendums, bacteria, consortiums, genera, mediums.

² Sampson, 26.

³ European Commission, *English Style Guide: A Handbook for Authors and Translators in the European Union Commission* (European Union, 2021), 8-10.

⁴ *Ibid.*, 19.

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... [1]

- Addenda, bacteriums, consortiums, genuses, media.

5. What of the following statements define plagiarism?

- Plagiarism is when the writer credits the author for any graph, statistics, or visual borrowed from any source.
- Plagiarism is when the writer uses a source of information without giving credit to the author of that source of information.⁵**
- Plagiarism is good academic writing practice.

Plagiarism is given credit to the author who produced the original work.

6. What is the correct format for author-date style citations?

- The author-date citations should include the author's last name, date, and relevant page numbers next to the reference in parenthesis.⁶**
- The Author-date citations should include the full name of the author and page numbers.
- The author-date citations should include the date, page, and the author name.
- The author-date citations do not have a specific format.

7. Define the components of the title of a dissertation.

⁵ Laurent Cleenewerck, and Kabiru Gulma, *ACA-401/ACA-401D Course pack Period 1*, Fourth Edition (Bangui: Euclid University, 2021), 34.

⁶ Kate L. Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations*. Chicago: Style for Students and Researchers, 9th ed. (Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 2018), 150.

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- The title should indicate the variables and participants included in the research.
- The title should indicate the variables, participants, and setting for the research, as well as the treatment, variables, participants, and setting for the research.**⁷
- The title should include the setting of the research and the participants.
- Depending on his objectives, the researcher decides what to include in the dissertation title.

8. According to Turabian, which statements describe guidelines for avoiding visual misrepresentations?

- Do not make a table or figure unnecessarily complex or misleading simple; use complex tables and graphs implying false correlations.
- Do not manipulate a scale to magnify or reduce a contrast; do not use a figure whose image distorts values; do not make a table or figure unnecessarily complex or misleadingly simple.**⁸
- Do not manipulate a scale to magnify or reduce contrast; use tridimensional and misleading simple graphs.
- Do not make a table or figure unnecessarily complex or misleading simple; use tridimensional graphs; do not use a figure whose image distorts values.

⁷ Sampson, 24.

⁸ Turabian, 102.

9. What of these statements describe reasons to mention the source used in your research?

- There is no need to mention the sources as far as the writer paraphrases the words.
- Plagiarism is wrong and unethical; it is unfair to take someone's work and not give them credit; it is a serious academic offense that can have serious consequences.**⁹
- Plagiarism is wrong and unethical; the writer can choose to mention some sources and not others.
- It is unfair to take someone's work and not give them credit; only books and journals should be mentioned.

10. Using the Turabian note style, how do you cite a book with two authors?

- Author #1's First and Last Names, Title of the Book: Subtitle of Book, page number(s).
 - Author # 1's First and Last Names, and Author #2's First and Last Names, Title of the Book, and page number(s).
- Author #2's First and Last Names, Title of Book: Subtitle of Book (Place of Publications: Publisher's Name and Date of Publication), Page number(s).

⁹ Cleenerwerck and Gulma, 34.

- Author # 1's First and Last Name and Author #2's First and Last Names, Title of Book: Subtitle of Book (Place of Publication: Publisher's name, Date of Publication), Page number(s).¹⁰**

¹⁰ Turabian, 150.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Gulma. *ACA-401/ACA-401D Course pack Period 1*. Fourth Edition Bangui: Euclid University, 2021.

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Turabian, Kate L. *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations, Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*. Edited by Wayne C. Booth, Gregory G. Colomb, Joseph Bizup, Williams Fitzgerald, and University of Chicago Press Staff. 9th ed. Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 2018.

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Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.

